

SUKUK (ISLAMIC BOND) AND INFRASTRUCTURE FINANCING IN SUB-SAHARAN AFRICAN COUNTRIES: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW OF THE GOALS, BENEFITS, CHALLENGES, AND RISK FACTORS

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Abstract- Infrastructures Development (ID) plays critical role in nation's development as a foundation for good governance, technological innovation, industrialization, and sustainable economic growth. However, Infrastructures Financing (IF) has become a wearisome task in Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries due to paltry budgetary allocation. Therefore, this calls for alternative sources of finance for IF with sukuk (Islamic bonds). Presently, Sukuk for IF is insignificant in most SSA countries, this has become a matter of concern to governments, policy makers, investors, and researchers. Moreover, the study examined the goals, benefits, challenges, and risk factors of sukuk instrument for IF in SSA countries. Exploratory research design was adopted for the study. The study revealed that Sukuk has become the instrument of choice for ID in both Muslim and Non-Muslim countries after global economic recession and financial crisis. Sukuk will improve positive externalities, enhances nation's external investment, increase tax revenue and economic growth, minimize urban congestion and unemployment. The study recommends that government should established relevant Islamic laws for sukuk capital market and a well-defined shariah governance framework to attract both local and foreign institutional investors. Similarly, personnel training and human capital development on Islamic finance should be considered. Also, sovereign sukuk should be issued at a price lower than that of conventional bonds for investors acceptance and attractiveness. Finally, public enlightenment on the benefits of sukuk should be intensified among non-Muslim faithful for acceptance and support.

Keywords: Conventional bonds, economic growth, good governance, Infrastructure Financing, Islamic laws, Sukuk

1.0 Introduction

Infrastructure's development plays critical role in nation's development. It is the foundation for good governance, employment opportunities, poverty eradication, and sustainable economic growth. It also fosters technological innovation, industrialization and citizens' standard of living, promote social and economic inclusion, and also enhance the successful implementation of 2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nation. Infrastructures are material public capital project (Nijkamp, 2000). Besides, Hirschman (1958) defines infrastructure as capital structure of public services. Infrastructures are the basic physical and organization structures, assets, or public goods that service the citizens without individuals' excludability but a means for effective economic development and citizens' standard of living. Infrastructure has characteristics of public goods at both national and local level, and it has long time frame, long-term economic growth, and it spawn a large number of diverse activities (Hem & Mayer, 2016). However, in Sub-Saharan African (SSA) region with forty-nine countries, an estimated population of 1.21billion, and at growth rate of 2.55%, infrastructure gap, decay or deficit has been a matter of concern to the government, policy makers and researchers, this contributes to economy downturn, high production cost, minimized Foreign Direct Investment inflows and financial capability.

Chinzara, Dessus and Dreyhaupt (2023) reported that infrastructures investment for SSA countries to achieve 2030 Sustainable Development Goals is approximately 7.1% of annual GDP from 2023 till 2030. But currently this stands at 3.5% of GDP. Similarly, African Development Bank asserts that annual funds required for Africa infrastructures deficit is US\$93billion till 2030. In the same vein, Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) stated that US\$71 trillion is required globally by 2030 for investment in roads, rails, telecommunications, electricity, seaports,

airports, water, and social infrastructures. However, to address infrastructures deficit in SSA countries, the region will require US\$130 to \$170 billion annually for infrastructures investment (AFDB, 2018; Juvonen *et al.* 2019).

Besides, Salaudeen (2021) argued that infrastructures deficit are the critical factors for nation's downturn, insecurity, high rate of unemployment, and increased brain drain from developing to developed countries. Infrastructure deficit at time arises due to population growth, urbanization, corruption, paltry budgetary allocations, and high indebtedness to foreign bodies like IMF, World Bank, Paris club, Development Banks, and other foreign agencies or governments. ADB (2023) also reported that instances like political instability, weak governance, insecurity, and corruption contributes to underinvestment in infrastructures. Likewise, the last COVID-19 Pandemic also revealed the worsen state of infrastructures in SSA countries in terms of quality, quantity, and accessibility. Ogunlana, Yaqub and Alhassan (2016), reported that development cannot lead to healthy living where enough funds are not channeled towards infrastructures development. Also, Adekoya (2019) opined that there exists in countries paltry budgetary allocations and insufficient funds for infrastructures development, this hinders country's ability to meet the 2030 sustainable development goals. Similarly, Biancone and Radwan (2018) opined that continuance reliance on public budgets to fund infrastructures development will remain a mirage, unstable and non-achievable.

Furthermore, Spohr, Wikstroma and Eriksson (2022) viewed that private sector collaboration is the practical solution to nations' infrastructure deficit. Therefore, the involvement of private sector in infrastructures financing becomes pertinent, but getting the right sources of finance remain a critical challenge (Arimoro, 2022). Although, the use of conventional bonds by the government is faced with various challenges likes stiff regulations and high interest rate, this at time led to high debt profile and project abandonment. Moreover, Alhassanz (2019); and Jiang (2019) reported that Japan and China have been the major financier of transportation system (rail and road) infrastructures development in SSA countries but mostly, this has unfavorable agreement or conditions which requires innovative financial mechanism. Above all, there is need to considered cheap and economical source of finance for infrastructures deficit in SSA countries. Alternatively, Sukuk (Islamic bonds) from Islamic banking and finance industry has been identified as a cheap instrument of mobilizing financial resources from the private sector to finance infrastructures development and salvage the prevailing infrastructures deficit.

Adekoya (2022) asserts that Islamic banking and fiancé is not a religious financial system but an ethical financial system meant for both Muslim and Non-Muslim individuals, corporate organizations, and governments. Sukuk is not a new term in Islamic finance, but a bond instrument structure based on shariah principles which avoid Gharar (unnecessary risk), Jahl (taking unfair advantage), Usury/Riba (interest), Rishwah (corruption), and Maisir (uncertainty/gambling). Sukuk or Islamic bonds are new instrument which can be used to channel private capital to public sector for infrastructures financing and solve the pertinent infrastructures gap in the region. Sukuk is an investment certificate that allow holder's the ownership of interest in an asset or pool of assets with annual receipts of income from the use of the assets. Likewise, sukuk have countless economic benefits in the areas of financial inclusion, economic diversification, infrastructures finance, and liquidity control (Abubakar & Baba, 2020).

According to AbdulKareem, Sadad bin Mahmud and AbdulGaniyy, (2020); Biancone and Radwan (2018); Lawal and Ajayi (2019), in many countries like Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, Indonesia, Qatar, United Kingdom, Germany, Pakistan, Bahrain, Singapore, and others, sukuks is used to source funds to finance infrastructures like roads, sea/air ports, railways, power plants, refinery, hospitals, schools, dams and other government projects which have positive impact on citizens' social wellbeing, nations economic growth and development. Studies had been conducted by researchers in the past on sukuk as independent variable with other dependent variables such as sukuk market development and economic growth (Ledhem, 2020; Yildirim, Yildirim & Diboglu, 2020; Altaleb & Alkhatib, 2016; Timilsina, Stern & Das, 2023); financing budget deficit (Baita & Mustafa, 2019); inevitability and relevance (Rahman, Abdul Halim, & Markom, 2021); sustainable development goal No 9 (Mohammad & Abduh, 2023). Also, infrastructure development such as infrastructure deficit in tertiary institutions (Duku, 2023); infrastructure development in Islamic countries (Iftikhar, 2022; Raham, Markon, Ab Halim, 2022; Gautama & Devi, 2021); and other independent variables like mutual funds and Islamic finance (Arimoro, Elgujja & Elgujja, 2022); pension fund (Adekoya, 2019; Anago, 2021); but with less focus on Sukuk (Islamic bond) and infrastructure financing in SSA countries. The objective of the study is to examine the goals, benefits, challenges and risk factors of using sukuk (Islamic bonds) for infrastructures financing in SSA countries to enhance economic growth, financial inclusion, good governance, and in general the well-being of the citizens. The paper is organized in sections, the next section is review of extant literatures, section three focuses on methodology, section four is extensive discussion, while section five is the summary, conclusion and recommendations.

2.0 Review of Extant Literature

2.1 Conceptual review

2.1.1 Infrastructure: The term “Infrastructure” originated from France in the 19th century as military installation. Frischmann (2005) defines infrastructure as physical resources systems made by human for public consumptions such as transportation systems (high way, railways, airline and ports system); communication systems (telephone network and postal service); governance systems (court and security); and basic public service and facilities (schools, hospital, and water systems). These forms of infrastructures are referred to as traditional infrastructure. Adequate and modern infrastructures create investment opportunities and drives inn foreign investment, increase productivity and enhance the wellbeing of the citizens, it also act as catalyst for economic, social, and political growth. Tooze (2018) asserts that a country like China is able to stabilizes its economy with adequate infrastructures financing. But, according to World Bank (2017) SSA countries have challenges of infrastructures deficit despite the region’s inherent geographical disadvantages and myriad of corruption. Traditional infrastructures are provided by the government or at time in conjunction with the private sector as Private Public Participation. Traditional infrastructure is non-excludability and nondiscriminatory public goods provided in an open and accessible manner to all citizens regardless of race, tribe, religion or faith.

2.1.2 Islamic Finance: Globally, Islamic finance has spread across financial spectrum of commercial banking, insurance, and capital markets with wider and increased opportunities for financial stability and economic growth in many countries. Despite the COVID-19 pandemic, Islamic finance industry continued to grow in recent years at composite average rate of 10.5% in 2020 and 2021 respectively. Besides, the global Islamic finance market has been predicted to grow by 10.2% between 2023 and 2028 with a global market size of \$2.23 billion and \$3.62 billion for 2023 and 2028 respectively. However, Iran has 29% market share of Islamic finance industry, followed by Saudi Arabia (25%), Malaysia (11%), United Arab Emirate (8%), Kuwait (6%), Qatar (6%), Turkey (2.6%), Bangladesh (2.1%), Indonesia (2%), and Bahrain (1.8%), while Africa region has the least with market share of 1.7% (Domat, 2024). Islamic finance industry is guided by global standard Islamic organization likes Academy of Organization of Islamic Conference (AOIC), Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB), Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI), Institutes of Islamic Liquidity Management (IILM), and Council of the Islamic Figh Academy. These bodies provide operational guidelines, product structuring, accounting, and the application of Islamic commercial Juris prudence to financial transactions. Islamic finance model has values for ethical, ecological, sustainable and social justice in line with shariah principles. Besides, Sukuk (Islamic bonds) instrument have become an important source of fiancé for large scale investment like asset acquisition, infrastructures development, and as working capital.

2.1.3 Sukuk: Sukuk was introduced in 1990 in Malaysia and today, the country remains the leader of the global sukuk market. Sukuk, is the plural of Sakk. The word “sukuk” comes from the Persian language “Jak” and Arabic language “Shak”. The word “Cheque” in English language originated from these words. Sukuk is an investment certificate that guarantee holder’s interest in ownership of an asset or pool of assets. The certificate guarantees the holder to receive stream of income over certain period of time from the use of an assets. Sukuk are form of securitization and Islamic bonds which are shariah compliant. International Islamic Financial Market (IIFM) defines sukuk (Islamic bonds) as commercial paper which provides an investor with ownership in an underlying asset. Besides, Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI) shariah standard 17(2), also defines sukuk as certificate of equal value represented by undivided shares in the ownership of tangible assets, usufructs and services of the ownership of the assets of particular projects or special investment activity. Similarly, Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB) (2018) defines sukuk as certificate that represent proportional undivided ownership right of intangible assets or pool of tangible assets or other type of assets. Normally, sukuk is structure like conventional bonds but with full compliance with the principles of shariah. In addition, sukuk investor’s income is not derived from debt and interest payment but from share of income from the underlying assets.

Sukuk can be categories into three, these are Equity based (Musharakah, Mudharabah); Leased based (Ijarah); and Sale based (Murabahah). However, AAOIFI identified 14 different types of sukuk but the most common among them are Ijarah, Murabaha, Musharak, Mudaraba, Salam, and Istisnaa. Also, Islamic Financial Market (IIFM) (2016) classified sukuk according to issuer status, of sovereign, corporate, and quasi- sovereign. Sovereign sukuk are issued by government and these usually dominated in local or foreign currency. Corporate sukuk are issued by corporate bodies, private or public limited companies apart from government and its agencies. Quasi- sovereign sukuk are issued by Government Corporation, these are indirectly or directly guarantee by the government. Parties to sukuk investment are mostly individuals, foreign investors, religious bodies, cooperative societies, and financial institutions such as (pension funds, asset managers, commercial banks, insurance/Takaful companies, and state investment companies). These parties can be categorized into three in sukuk contract, these are the originator, the trustee or SPV, and the investors. In recent time, Sukuk markets have grown globally with much domination in the Persian Gulf Corporation and South East Asian Countries. Similarly, Muslim dominated countries like Malaysia, Indonesia, Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, Bahrain, United Arab Emirates, Qatar, Pakistan, and Turkey have become the leading global sukuk markets. However, there

have been an increase for Islamic finance and sukuk instrument in non-Muslim countries like United Kingdom, United State of America, Germany, Japan, Nigeria, South Africa, Hong Kong, Singapore, and Luxembourg. LSEG Business (2022) reported that sukuk issued from entities based of 21 countries in 2021 has Malaysia as leader with \$72.6 billion, followed by Saudi Arabia \$49.9 billion and Indonesia \$23.4 billion.

2.1.4 Benefits of issuing Sukuk in Sub-Saharan Africa countries

1. To diversify the sources of government finances and enhance Direct Foreign Investment.
2. To provide investors the ample opportunity to invest in government securities
3. To provide funds for social, economic, and political infrastructural projects.
4. To achieve a greater level of financial inclusion.
5. To curtail inflation
6. To fosters financial stability, economic growth and employment opportunities.
7. To enable investors', have tax free advantage on income from sukuk investment and also to use sukuk certificate as collateral for interest free loan.
8. To minimize foreign loans or debts with high ridding interest.
9. To provide investment opportunity for Islamic Banks to invest their idle funds. This will increase bank's profitability and the statutory liquidity ratio with Central Bank.
10. To create opportunity for Muslim community or individuals to invest in Shariah compliant instrument.

2.1.5 Differences between Sukuk and Conventional Bonds

S/N	Sukuk	Conventional Bonds
1	It represents ownership of interest in defined or existing assets	It represents pure debt obligation that is due from the issuer.
2	Funds raised must be used only for intended and ethical purpose	Funds raised from bonds can be used to finance any legal purpose
3	Sukuk sales represent sale of a portion of asset	Bond sale is a sale of debt
4	Sukuk prices depend on the market value of underlying asset.	Bonds prices depends on the credit worthiness of the issuer.
5	Sukuk issuance are backed with Islamic laws and regulations.	Bonds issuance are backed with civil/legal laws.
6	Profit are shared as means of return to holders	Bonds has a fixed coupon interest rate to holders.
7	Capital and performance are not contractually guarantee.	Capital and performance are contractually guarantee.
8	Underlying assets must be shariah compliant in terms of nature and use.	Bonds transaction need not to be Islamic ally permissible in its jurisdiction

2.1.6 Challenges of sukuk market in Sub-Saharan African Countries

1. Lack of proper awareness especially for non-Muslim's individuals on the economic and social benefits of sukuk to the nation and the citizens.
2. Lack of regulatory and legal framework for sukuk issuance, capital market, and operation. This hinders the smooth issuance and trading of sukuk bonds.
3. Religious misconception among non-Muslim faith. This is the erroneous believe among them of Islamizing a country with the adoption of Islamic finance.
4. Shortage of Islamic Banks to market and promote the issuance of sukuk and personnel with knowledge on Islamic laws for monitoring shariah compliance in banks.
5. Sukuk has operational challenge from knowledge and technical strategic incompetency.
6. Persistent political instability and weak institutional framework.
7. Corruption as it affects abandoned projects. This limit financing capital project with sukuk due to uncertainty of returns for sukuk prospective investors.

2.1.7 Types of sukuk

1. Mudarabah- it is a form of partnership. It is a contract of two parties on commercial activities with agreement of profit sharing at the ratio of the capital contributed while any loss that arises will be borne only by the fund provider.
2. Musharakah- Joint ventures. It is a form of equity finance. Here, parties contributed money to projects and any profit or loss that arises from the projects are shared at the ratio of capital contributed.
3. Murabahah- this is also known as cost plus financing. It is a purchasing financing method which builds markup on selling price for a postponed payment.

4. Salam- prepayment for asset to be delivered in the future
5. Istisna- finance for asset under construction or those yet to be built.
6. Ijarah- this is the best and common option for infrastructure finance. It is a lease agreement that gives the lessee the option to purchase asset at the end of lease agreement.

2.1.8 Ijarah Sukuk

Ijarah (Rent) sukuk is an agreement between two parties, the lessor (Mujir) and the lessee (Mustajir). Ijarah sukuk is used to finance economic, social and political infrastructures that will add value to the nation's economic development and citizens' standard of living. Ijarah sukuk has now become an important alternative source of finance from Islamic finance industry for both public and private sectors. The Ijarah sukuk market has grown rapidly in terms of size, numbers patronages, and values as viable sources of finance for infrastructures development. Ijarah sukuk issuance process involve three parties, these are: the originator, sukuk holders, and Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV). Ijarah sukuk are issued to investors through SPV. The SPV thereafter form a trust company which acts as trustee on behalf of the investors. Moreover, SPV acting as trustee purchase asset from the originator. Thereafter, SPV leased the asset to the originator for an agreed time frame as stated in the contractual document. The originator or lessee pays rental fee on regular basis to SPV, this represent sukuk payments. Similarly, SPV makes regular payments on sukuk to the investors till maturity date when the principal amounts will be redeemed. Many developed and developing countries like United Kingdom, Japan, Singapore, Indonesia, Malaysia, South Africa, Nigeria, and Qatar had issued Ijarah sukuk for infrastructures development.

2.2 Theoretical Review

The study anchored on theory of infrastructure-led development and theory of political economy.

2.2.1 Theory of infrastructure- led development – the theory sees infrastructure as engine for economic growth and development. According to Agenor (2010) insufficient infrastructure hinders or limit economic growth and development in most developing countries. However, Horner *et al.* (2018) reported that infrastructure led development highlight the durability of globalization, expansion of emerging markets, and frontier economy. Presently, infrastructures led development in SSA countries are driven by global growth with the coalition of: development banks, multinational corporation, multilateral government institutions, and other developed countries like China, Japan, and United State of America (Schindler & Kanai, 2021). Globally, there has been growing global consensus on the merit of large-scale infrastructure such as bridges, roads, telecommunication, airports, seaports, hospitals, schools, dams, and others towards the economic growth of a nation. Besides, African Development Bank (AfDB) (2018) asserts that African countries can transform into global economy by investing into well targeted infrastructures to support competitive industries and becomes industrialized nations.

2.2.2 Theory of political economy- Political economy started in the 18th century as the theory and practice of economics affair. This refers to the science of wealth, it deals with man or government effort to source for his needs and desires. According to Borrooah, (1985), political economy theory is the complexity of interaction between economic and political behaviour. The theory gives priority to the understanding of social change and historical transformation within the society. Weingast and Wittman (2008) viewed political economy as interdisciplinary studies of law, political science, and economics to explain how political, economic, and environmental system (socialist, capitalist or mixed) influenced each other. Besides, Islamic economy started in 1950s when Muslims dominated countries commenced steps to build economic system that is in line with the principles of Shariah. Choudhury (1997) viewed Islamic political economy as a distinct Epistemology with shariah principles. Also, Asutay (2007) viewed Islamic economics system as an approach that cares about human and ensure ethical values where Islamic bank act as a unit of the Islamic economics model.

2.3 Empirical review

Sulaiman and Rabi (2023); Sani, Nasir and Bakare (2022) studied the impact of sukuk finance on infrastructures financing in Nigeria. The study revealed that sukuk have significant impact on infrastructures financing than external loans. Similarly, Rahman, Markom and Ab Halim (2022) looked at the economic infrastructural development in Bangladesh with sukuk financing. The study concluded that sukuk is a good source of finance for infrastructural development. Furthermore, Arimoro, Elgujja and Elgujja (2022) examined the role of Islamic finance of mutual fund for public infrastructure in Sub-Saharan Africa. The study revealed that paltry budgetary allocation limit infrastructures development and therefore, recommends the use of Islamic finance mutual funds for infrastructure development. In addition, Salaudeen (2021) investigated the use of sukuk instrument for infrastructural development in Nigeria. The study concluded that adoption of sukuk instrument for infrastructure development in the country is a good alternative financing option.

Moreover, Abubakar *et al.* (2020) investigated sukuk as alternative source of finance for capital projects in Nigeria. The study revealed a positive synergy between sukuk and budget in addressing infrastructural challenges in Nigeria. In the same vein, Abdulkareem, Sada bin Mahmud and Ali (2021) looked at factors that influence Nigerians to invest in sukuk instrument. The study reported that attitude, subjective norms, religious belief are key factors that influence Nigerian investor to invest in sukuk (Islamic bonds). Besides, Ogunbado (2019) examined sukuk as source of finance for infrastructure development in Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) members' countries. The study revealed that sukuk remain a better financing option for mega projects in OIC member's countries. Furthermore, Abdurraheem and Naim (2018) studied the application of sukuk for infrastructure financing in Sub-Saharan African countries. The study revealed that sukuk instrument is new in SSA countries. Therefore, using sukuk instrument for infrastructures development in the region will minimized huge sovereign debts that arises from conventional bond.

Duku (2023) examined sukuk Murabahah as mechanism for financing infrastructure deficit in Nigerian tertiary institutions. The study revealed that murabahah sukuk as means of finance for infrastructure development in tertiary institutions will uplift there standard. Moreover, Iftikhar (2022) studied block-chain based retail sukuk and infrastructure development in Pakistan. The study concluded that good governance, legal, and regulatory support, will make sukuk a good instrument to finance infrastructures development and support the 2030 sustainable development goals. In addition, Mohammad and Abduh (2022) examined the role of Islamic finance in achieving the sustainable development goals (SDGS) No 9. The study revealed that sukuk instrument will enhance SDGS infrastructural and technological development, and achieve sustainable industrialization.

Also, Gautama and Dewi (2021) studied the significances of sukuk for road infrastructures development in Indonesia. The study revealed that sukuk instrument enhances road infrastructures development. Furthermore, Abdulkareem, Sada bin Mahmud and AbdulGaniyy (2021) examined sukuk and infrastructures development with focus on abandoned projects in Nigeria. The study revealed that sukuk remain a reliable financing instrument to aid the completion of abandoned projects in Nigeria. In the same vein, Rahman, Abdul Halim, and Markom (2021) studied the inevitability and relevancy of sukuk in Bangladesh. The study revealed individual option for sukuk depends on investor's philosophy, infrastructures, economic, legal and regulatory framework. Furthermore, Baita and Mustafa (2019) looked at economics benefit of using sukuk to finance budget deficits in Nigeria. The study revealed that sukuk remain a viable option to conventional bonds for funding budgetary deficit, infrastructures deficit, and promotion of fiscal sustainability.

3.0 Methodology

The study employed exploratory research design. This involves systematic review of literatures, analyses, and conclusions. These are drawn from finance, accounting and economics books, journals and other publications to enhance the frontiers of knowledge.

4.0 Extensive Discussion

4.1 Infrastructure deficit and sukuk significance

Infrastructure promotes economic growth, minimized production cost, enhance productivity of human capital, and improve the rate of return on capital investment. Agenor (2010) opined that long run development through public infrastructure is the engine room for country's economic growth while infrastructures deficit retards economic growth and development in SSA countries. According to Africa's pulse (2023), economic growth index in SSA countries for 2022 and 2023 were 3.6% and 2.5% respectively but with a projection of 3.7% and 4.1% for 2024 and 2025 respectively. However, this growth index is expected to be driven by infrastructures development and Sukuk (Islamic bonds) of Islamic finance can be adopted. Islamic financial industry has been in operation for many years in Muslim dominated countries like Malaysia, Indonesia, Sudan, Pakistan, Brunei, Saudi Arabia, Bahrain, Qatar, Oman, and United Arab Emirates. Also, it has spread to other non-Muslim dominated countries like United Kingdom, Germany, Hong Kong, and Luxembourg. Moreover, using Sukuk to finance infrastructures deficit in SSA countries remain a viable option going by its success story from other countries and regions of the world. In addition, there are numbers of prospective investors from South East and Middle East Asia like Indonesia and Malaysia who are interested to invest in SSA countries.

According to Abdurraheem and Naim (2018), SSA region suffers huge infrastructures deficit due to immense funding gap. Besides, infrastructure deficit in SSA countries retards economic growth and also contributes to the persistent poverty prevailing in the region. AfDB (2018) reported that Africa countries required annual investment of US\$67.6 to US\$170 billion for infrastructures financing to cover the infrastructure deficit of at least US\$93.3billion in the region. However, insufficient infrastructures in SSA region remain a major obstacle to the region's development. In SSA countries, only 16% of the region roads are paved while less than 20% of the citizens have access to electricity. Similarly, Foster and Briceno-Garmendia (2010) reported that electricity access in SSA low-income countries is 16%,

while in other similar developing countries 41%. Also, road access and transportation in SSA countries have low density of paved road of 31km per 1000 km while in similar low income developing countries 134 km per 1000 km. Likewise, the internet usage rate in SSA countries is 6% while 40% in similar low income developing countries (Collier & Cust, 2015).

Besides, Information Communication Technology (ICT) and globalization have significantly contributed to the economic growth of developed countries but this has less impact on the economies of SSA countries. Moreover, Timilsina, Stern and Das (2023) argued that power and telecommunication have large long-run positive effects on countries GDP while, Kouladoum (2023); and Ofori and Asongu (2021) also concluded that digital infrastructures development has positive inclusive growth in the SSA countries' economies. Therefore, adequate investment on ICT will ensure that transaction and information cost are minimized, employment opportunity are created, and poverty rate are reduced (Abor, Amidu & Issahaku, 2018; Nchofoung & Asongu, 2022). In addition, government investment on water supply, sanitation, and electricity would have positive and significant impact on economic growth and development (Abdullahi & Sieng, 2023). Above all, infrastructure is key to nation's development but annual paltry budgetary allocation limit infrastructures development. Therefore, consideration for alternative sources of finance like sukuk (Islamic bonds) becomes important.

In SSA region, at least eight countries namely Gambia, Nigeria, Ivory Coast, Mali, Senegal, Sudan, Togo, South Africa and others have embraced sukuk instrument as sources of finance. Sudan and Gambia issued sukuk in the late 2000s as mechanism to managed Central Bank reserves. In Nigeria, the first ₦11.4billion sukuk bond was issued by Osun State Government (OSG) in 2013, called Osun Ijarah sukuk, for the building of ten schools to enhance educational facilities. Senegal starts sukuk issuance in 2014 with four years sukuk terms of 100 billion CFA franc. Cote d'ivoire in 2015 and 2016 with five year and seven years sukuk of 150 billion CFA franc each respectively. Also, South Africa in 2014 issued \$500 million six years sukuk, and other countries have followed in the region.

4.2 Nigeria perspective

Nigeria has been experiencing infrastructures deficit in area of health facilities, paved road, rail systems, power supply, security, water supply, and educational facilities due to annual financing gap, corruption, paltry budgetary allocation, and huge debt servicing. Also, high interest rate emanating from loan agreement from World Bank, International Monetary Fund (IMF), Paris Club and other countries have contributed to infrastructures deficit and projects abandonment. However, to avert this trends, alternative and cheap source of finance like sukuk (Islamic bond) becomes important and reliable. Nigeria embraced this Islamic finance instrument (sukuk) in 2013 through ₦11.4billion sukuk bond issued by Osun State Government (OSG) to finance the construction of ten schools. This was called Osun Ijarah sukuk and to achieve this, a company called Osun State Sukuk Company was established as Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV). Thereafter in 2013, the Security and Exchange Commission (SEC) formulated and issued the relevant guidelines, laws, and frameworks that guides the issuance and operation of sukuk in Nigeria. The SEC laws, guidelines, and frameworks gives the Federal Government of Nigeria the power and opportunities to issue sovereign sukuk.

The first sovereign sukuk of ₦100billion (16.47% rate of return) 7years was issued on 14th September, 2017 to funds twenty-five critical roads across the six geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The second batch of ₦100billion (15.443% rate of return) 7years was issued in 6th December, 2018 through Debt Management Office (DMO). On 21st May, 2020, the third batch of ₦150billion (11.2% rate of return) 7years Ijarah sukuk was issued, to fund forty-four roads in the six geopolitical zone of Nigeria, this was oversubscribed by ₦519.12billion. Similarly, the fourth sukuk of ₦250billion (12.8% rate of return) 10years was issued in 16th December, 2021, this was also oversubscribed by 346%. On 21st November, 2022, the Federal government further issued ₦100billion at ₦1000 per unit of 10years 15.64% Ijarah Sukuk due 2032. This was upsized to ₦130 billion due to oversubscription by 165%. However, on 11th October, 2023, additional ₦150 billion (15.75% rate of return) 10years Ijarah sukuk was issued, this was also oversubscribed by 435%. This trend of issuance shows the acceptance of sukuk as alternative instrument for financing infrastructures development but this comes with various risk factors.

4.3 Sukuk Risk Factors with reference to Nigeria

1. Country Risk

Political Risk – Nigeria has witnessed many political instabilities since 1960 Independence Day. After many years of military rules, the country returned to democratically elected government in 1999. Thereafter, a transfer of power from one democratically elected government to another for the past 25years. However, insecurity remains a major challenge for the government. There has been insecurity and insurgency of religious attacks, banditry and kidnapping across the country. These pose a threat to the political and economic stability of the nation. It also affects revenue generation,

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), and investment opportunities in critical sectors. This risk remains a critical factor to the success of sukuk instrument even as reference in other SSA countries.

2. Macro-Economic Risk

(a) Economic Risk – Nigeria economy mostly depends on crude oil sales for foreign exchange earnings. Likewise other SSA countries depends on one mineral resources for foreign earnings. Country's dependence on mineral resources is sensitive to price changes at the global market. This was experienced in 2020 during the COVID-19 pandemic when there were global dropped in demands and prices of goods and services. Besides, Nigeria has economic challenge of "Doing Business" with high rate of bureaucracy, corruption and bribery as major impediments, this affects the country economic growth and social development. World Bank report of Doing Business index in Nigeria for 2019 was 146 while that for 2020-2023 index stand at 131 out of 190 countries respectively. Also, naira depreciation and high interest rate have become impediment to the nation economy, governance, and low tax revenue. This risk remains a key factor to the adoption of sukuk as financing option to salvage infrastructures deficit in Nigeria and other SSA countries.

(b) Inflation Risk – rate of inflation has become very high and this reduces the purchasing power of investor's cash flow. Potential investors from local environment are faced with challenges of diminished naira value. In Nigeria, inflation rate on the prices of goods and services charged for Value Added Tax (VAT) increases from 15.99% in 2021 to 21.09% in 2022. Likewise, the nation inflation rate increases from 18.34% in 2021 to 23.72% and 28.99% in 2022 and 2023 respectively, and as high as 29.9% in 2024 (NBS, 2024). However, government has designed strategy to curb the rising inflation and keep it at bay but where inflation continue to rise, it will reduce investment of fund in sukuk. High rate of inflation will have negative impact on infrastructures and nation's development.

3. Sukuk Related Risk

(a) Credit Risk – this is the risk associated with the issuer. It is the risk of default of annual rental payments and payment of the principal sum at maturity date. Therefore, this calls for due diligence on issuer credit worthiness.

(b) Regulatory Risk – Sukuk is governed by laws of the nation and issued in line with the prevailing legislative framework. However, changes in statutory and regulatory environment can leads to amendment to existing laws and regulations, this might affect implementation, success, and issuance of sukuk. Therefore, standard regulatory framework will enhance the implementation of sukuk (Islamic bonds).

(c) Sharia Non-Compliance Risk – sukuk is issued in line with shariah laws and guidelines. It is structured by expert in Islamic finance and guided by shariah board law and regulations of Ijarah structure. This must be strictly followed in implementation. However, non-compliance to shariah laws and process will derailed its purpose and objectives. Moreover, public enlightenment on the importance of the sukuk to other faith believers becomes pertinent and importance.

5.0 Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Summary and Conclusion

Infrastructure is a pillar to economic growth; therefore, a nation cannot develop without adequate investment in infrastructures. Anago (2021) and Hassan (2022) opined that even COVID-19 pandemic and its impacts has contributed more pressure on the nation's budgetary allocation, this led to annual paltry allocation to infrastructures development in SSA countries. However, AFDB (2018); Juvonen *et al.* (2019) opined that to address infrastructure deficit in SSA countries, the region will require US\$130 to \$170 billion annually for infrastructures investment. Sukuk has become the instrument of choice for infrastructure development in both Muslim and Non-Muslim countries after global economic recession and financial crisis. Moreover, financing infrastructures with cheaper sources of finance like sukuk (Islamic Bonds) will foster SSA countries development and also reduce infrastructure deficit pertinent in the region (Baita & Mustafa, 2019; Calderon, Cantu & Chuhan-Pole, 2018). In addition, Sovereign sukuk for infrastructures development in SSA countries will improve positive externalities, enhances nation's external investment, increase tax revenues, and citizens' wellbeing. Similarly, adequate funding of public infrastructures will reduce urban congestion, crimes and insecurity, unemployment rate, and also increases economic growth and development. Besides, with numbers of potential investors from Asian countries and their appetite for diversification via sukuk investment and infrastructure financing in SSA countries, this will reduce infrastructures deficit and huge debts that arises from conventional bonds, develop and support 2030 sustainable development, and completion of abandoned projects in SSA countries. Also, the great numbers of Muslim in SSA countries and their individual attitudes, subjective norms and religious faith/belief are critical factors for sukuk investment and demand for shariah compliant products or service. In addition, the success of sukuk in many countries like Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, Indonesia, Qatar, United Kingdom, Germany, Pakistan, Bahrain, Singapore, and others for infrastructures financing like roads, ports, railways, power plants, refinery, hospitals, schools, dams and other government projects will aid the acceptance of sukuk in SSA countries (AbdulKareem, Sadad bin Mahmud & AbdulGaniyy, 2020; Biancone and Radwan, 2018; Lawal and Ajayi, 2019).

5.2 Recommendations

To solve infrastructure deficit, gap or decay in SSA countries, government should consider Islamic finance as alternative sources of finance for key infrastructures that will have positive impact on the growth and development of the country and the wellbeing of the citizens. Moreover, legal and institutional framework on Islamic finance should be designed to attract both local and foreign institutional investors. Similarly, SSA countries should established the relevant Islamic laws and guidelines for sukuk capital market and Islamic products. This will assist to standardized the activities of sukuk market, Islamic financial stability, and sukuk bond as investment securities. Also, SSA countries should established well-defined shariah governance framework that will align with Islamic financial policy and the institutions likes Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB), Islamic Development Bank (IDB), Islamic Financial Stability Forum (IFSF), and International Islamic Liquidity Management Corporation (IILM). In addition, personnel training and human capital development on Islamic finance, capital market operations, and shariah laws interpretation should be considered. Moreover, sovereign sukuk (Islamic bonds) should be issued at a price lower than conventional bonds for investors acceptability and attractiveness. Besides, the use of information technology for accessibility of market information for investors' decision remain critical as this will boost liquidity and enhance transparency in sukuk issuance and redemption. Furthermore, public enlightenment on the benefits of sukuk should be intensified among non-Muslim faithful for acceptance, consideration and support.

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